

Evaluation of Overtourism in the Island of Crete, Greece

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ABSTRACT:

Overtourism describes the phenomenon where the large number of tourists overwhelm a destination, negatively affecting local communities, the environment, and visitor experiences. It has become a global issue in many popular tourism destinations in recent years. Overtourism has multiple causes and many undesired environmental, economic and social impacts. An evaluation of overtourism in the island of Crete, Greece has been realized estimating the tourism density and tourism intensity. During 2023 6,327,366 visitors arrived in Crete while their mean residence time was 5.43 days. Various indexes for assessing overtourism have been proposed. The tourism density in 2023 in Crete has been evaluated at 4,120 bed-nights/km² while its tourism intensity at 55.63 bed-nights/resident. These values are well above the mean global and EU average. The number of visitors in Crete are growing constantly every year while the majority of tourism infrastructure is concentrated in the north coastline of the island where the large towns are located. Therefore, the cultural and historical monuments, the natural fragile ecosystems and the main towns in Crete are overcrowded particularly during the summer months. The high number of tourists in the island threatens the unique ecosystems and its historical monuments utilizing its limited natural resources. Consequently, the local tourism stakeholders should develop appropriate measures and policies decreasing the negative consequences of tourism and increasing the sustainability of the prosperous tourism industry in Crete.

Keywords: causes, Crete-Greece, environmental impacts, overtourism, social impacts, tourism indicators.

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INTRODUCTION

The concept of overtourism has been developed the last few years and is related with the negative impacts of tourism in popular tourism destinations [1-5]. Various studies have indicated various causes which contribute to overtourism while there are many difficulties for its mitigation and prevention [6,7]. Overtourism has adverse environmental, economic and social impacts in tourism destinations [8-11]. Several indexes have been used for measuring overtourism [4,12]. The island of Crete, Greece, located in Eastern Mediterranean basin, is a popular global tourism destination with increasing flows of visitors. The characteristics of the tourism industry in Crete have been estimated [13-14].

The aim of the current work is to analyze and assess overtourism in the island of Crete, Greece.

The structure of the text is as follows: After the literature survey the concepts of overtourism and of overcrowded destinations are analyzed. In the following sections the methods and the indicators for assessing overtourism as well as its undesired impacts are stated. After that the tourism industry in Crete and the evaluation of overtourism in the island are mentioned. The text ends with discussion of the findings, the conclusions drawn and the citation of the references used.

The present study covers the gap regarding the estimation of overtourism in Crete, Greece while it has innovative aspects due to lack of similar studies related to overtourism in popular tourism destinations in Mediterranean basin as well as in the island of Crete. The work could be useful to policy makers and to stakeholders of the tourism industry in Crete who should try to prevent overtourism in the island reducing its undesired and harmful impacts on the local ecosystems and the society.

LITERATURE SURVEY

The negative environmental, social and cultural impacts of overtourism in popular tourism destinations mainly in Mediterranean region have been studied [8]. The author stated that overtourism increases water consumption, air pollution and production of wastes. It also has negative effects in the fragile ecosystems at various destinations. She mentioned that overtourism increases the food prices and the rentals of houses. Additionally, it causes housing shortages in destination areas. The overtourism, its implications and perspectives have been studied [6]. The authors stated that the development of new technologies and the low-cost airlines have increased the number of tourists worldwide who are expected to be around 2 billion by 2030. They also mentioned that the increased number of tourists in several popular destinations have undesired environmental, social and cultural impacts. The sustainability of overtourism has been studied [15]. The author has developed a multidisciplinary approach of tourism including: a) the economic environment, b) the socio-political environment, and c) the ecological environment. She also mentioned that, in general, overtourism means unsustainable tourism. Additionally, she stated the concepts of tourism capacity in a tourism destination, of tourismphobia, and of responsible tourism. The phenomena of overtourism have been reviewed [1]. The authors stated that overtourism is the result of many parameters which together create a “tourism storm” in several destinations. They also mentioned that there are many difficulties in mitigating and preventing overtourism in the near future. The overtourism and tourismphobia have been studied [2]. The authors reviewing the existing literature stated that the concepts of overtourism and tourismphobia have emerged in the last few years. They also mentioned that many tourism destinations located in Europe express their concerns with the pressures caused by excess tourism in urban areas and cities. The concept of overtourism has been studied [3]. The author stated that “overtourism describes destinations where locals and tourists feel that there are too many visitors and the quality of life of the locals and the quality of experience by the tourists has been deteriorated unacceptably”. He also mentioned that there are many causes of overtourism in several destinations while the public authorities play an important role in managing tourism. The impacts of overtourism on local residents in a heritage city have been studied [9]. The authors stated that local residents believe that excess tourism offers the possibility to become entrepreneurs. They also mentioned that overtourism has positive and negative impacts to local residents. The impacts of overtourism at city level have been examined [10]. The authors stated that the concept of overtourism is multidimensional and complex. They also mentioned that overtourism is not well conceptualized while its impacts are diverse, complex and multifaced. The indexes for assessing overtourism have been studied [16]. The authors stated several indicators for measuring overtourism which have been proposed by: a) Peeters et al, 2018 on behalf of EU TRAN Committee, b) McKinsey company, c) EU, and d) Lucerne University. The literature related with overtourism measurement has been reviewed [12]. The authors stated that overtourism is a complex multidisciplinary and multidimensional phenomenon while it is difficult to develop a simple methodology for its measurement. They also mentioned that the first step to assess overtourism is to develop a set of broadly accepted indicators which can be easily evaluated. The risk of overtourism in Tunisia has been assessed [17]. The authors stated that Tunisia is a popular global tourism destination and the negative effects of tourism should be prevented. The authors assessed the risk of overtourism in the country based on tourism density and tourism intensity identifying the areas in Tunisia with high risk of overtourism. The accommodation density in coastal tourism areas in insular destinations from the perspective of overtourism has been analyzed [18]. The authors stated that the most relevant indicator to measure overtourism is tourism density. They also mentioned that the use of tourism density as a parameter to assess the urban saturation in several destinations has many weaknesses and the level of satisfaction of tourists should be taken into account. The overtourism in Fjords, Norway has been studied [19]. The authors stated that

destination marketing organizations pursue strategies to stimulate arrivals which might cause conflicts with local residents. They proposed that the development of local small-scale and more sustainable experiences of tourists can contribute to economic growth without increasing the number of arrivals. The overtourism in Europe has been analyzed [4]. The authors stated the most important indicators for measuring overtourism. They also mentioned the multidimensional causes and the multiple economic, social and environmental impacts of overtourism analyzing the concept of carrying capacity in tourism destinations. The problem of overtourism has been analyzed [20]. It is mentioned that tourism has many benefits beyond simple economic growth. There are several solutions to cope with overtourism which is a seasonal problem for a small number of destinations. The prevention of overtourism has been analyzed [21]. It is stated that radical measures have been taken in few destinations such as Venice, Barcelona and Amsterdam to cope with overtourism. The solutions to this problem must be tailor-made to the unique destination including its better management. Tourism degrowth is a remedy to overtourism although the local tourism stakeholders will not accept it easily. The economic performance of the tourism industry in Crete has been analyzed [13]. The authors stated that only half of the hotels in Crete use economic indicators to assess their performance. They also mentioned that their operating cost is in the range of 10-33 €/bed-night while their breakeven occupancy rate is at 38%. The overtourism in the island of Crete has been studied [14]. The author estimated the tourism density at 2,941 bed-nights per km² and the and tourism intensity at 38.6 bed-nights per resident in 2016. He also mentioned that the island of Crete is an overcrowded tourism destination while its tourism density and tourism intensity are above the EU and global average. The mitigation and compensation of CO₂ emissions due to international tourism in Crete have been studied [22]. The author estimated the carbon intensity of the Cretan tourism industry at 0.562 kgCO₂/€ which is in the same range of values reported for other EU countries. A roadmap for a greener, inclusive and resilient tourism in the Mediterranean region has been published [23]. The report stated that tourism in Mediterranean basin faces a triple crisis comprising: a) climate change, b) biodiversity loss, and c) environmental pollution. Additionally, it faces external disruptions such as the Covid-19 pandemic and geopolitical conflicts. The impacts of overtourism have been examined [11]. The authors stated that overtourism is a relatively new term in the public and academic debate describing the negative consequences of tourism. She mentioned the importance of social carrying capacity in tourism destinations pointing out that there is still no specific policies for dealing with overtourism. The effects of overtourism on residents' perceptions in Alcudia, Majorca, Spain have been studied [24]. The authors stated that 65% of the residents perceived the destination as overcrowded while 57% of them considered it as a good place to live. They also mentioned that the good management of the destination and the positive tourists' behavior have reduced the negative aspects of overtourism. The phenomena of overtourism and tourismphobia have been analyzed [25]. The authors stated that during the last four decades a lot of concern has been developed regarding the antagonistic relationships between locals and tourists, the tourism area life cycle and the carrying capacity of tourism destinations. They also mentioned that the terms "overtourism" and "tourismphobia" have their genesis in the rapid unfolding of unsustainable mass tourism practices which negatively affect the quality of life of residents as well as the local fragile ecosystems and the historical monuments. The reasons and the consequences of overtourism in contemporary cities have been investigated [7]. The author stated that the growing number of tourists, the availability of cheap flights and mistakes in cities' management contribute to overtourism. Additional causes of overtourism are the high popularity of city tourism and the shift from 3S (Sea, Sun and Sand) to 3E (Education, Experience and Entertainment) tourism. The phenomenon of overtourism has been studied [5]. The authors examined whether there is a consensus among tourism stakeholders regarding the definition of overtourism and its positive and negative impacts. They analyzed the answers of questionnaires from 54 participants. All of them agreed regarding the definition of overtourism while they emphasized the terms "carrying capacity" and "decrease in quality of life". Some of the participants mentioned that overtourism might not be a problem since it generates higher incomes at destinations. The visitor-resident relations in destinations characterized by overtourism has been studied [26]. The authors stated that while almost all tourism destinations seek to increase the flow of tourists less attention is paid in balancing the relation among visitors and residents which is necessary to promote sustainable tourism. They also mentioned that policy makers should try to avoid deterioration of the tourists-residents' relations exceeding the destination's social carrying capacity in order to make tourism more sustainable. The

overtourism in European cities has been analyzed [27]. The author stated that overtourism is always a matter of perceptions being a relative rather than an absolute phenomenon. He also mentioned that an answer to overtourism is the dispersal of tourists both in space and in time. Other strategies coping with overtourism are related with better understanding of the carrying capacity of cities, the flows of visitors and the behavior of different types of tourists. A digital response system for overtourism mitigation in Dubrovnic, Croatia has been studied [28]. The authors stated that successful responses to overtourism are related with the tourism carrying capacity of cities. They also mentioned that the use of modern technologies including measuring and monitoring tourist flows and the carrying capacity in cities can assist in the minimization of the negative effects of overtourism. The development of innovative and sustainable practices in tourism in Algrave, Portugal has been described [29]. The authors stated that Algrave region has promoted tourism sustainability based on three pillars, environmental, economic and social. The region has improved the water management and has developed sustainable agricultural practices supporting the cultivation of carob tree. They also mentioned that Algrave tries to promote tourism all over the year and to redevelop the sea front focusing on urban planning. The decarbonization of the tourism sector focusing on Queens town, New Zealand has been studied [30]. The author stated that the city has developed a regenerative tourism plan for 2030 which is based on three pillars comprising: a) empowerment of communities and enhancement of visitors' experiences, b) restoration of the environment and decarbonization of the tourism economy, and c) building economic resilience, capability and productivity.

THE CONCEPT OF OVERTOURISM

Overtourism, the phenomenon where tourist numbers overwhelm a destination, negatively affecting local communities, the environment, and visitor experiences, has become a global issue in recent years. Several factors contribute to overtourism, ranging from economic incentives and the rise of budget travel to technological advancements and social media trends. Overtourism describes the situation in which the impact of tourism at certain times and in certain locations exceeds physical, ecological, social, economic, psychological and/or political thresholds [4]. Other researchers consider that overtourism describes destinations where hosts of guests, locals or visitors, feel that there are too many visitors and that the quality of life in the area or the quality of experience has deteriorated unacceptably [3]. One of the primary causes of overtourism is the rapid expansion of the global travel industry. Increased accessibility to affordable transportation, particularly through budget airlines and cheaper travel options, has enabled more people to explore destinations that were once difficult to reach. Countries with tourism-driven economies have eagerly welcomed this influx, developing infrastructure to accommodate growing numbers of visitors. However, in many cases, this has exceeded the capacity of local resources and infrastructure, resulting in overcrowded streets, damaged ecosystems, and strained public services. Another significant factor is the rise of social media, which has transformed the way people choose travel destinations. Platforms like Instagram, Facebook, and TikTok have created a culture of "destination marketing," where picturesque locales become viral, driving tourists to specific sites in droves. The constant sharing of idealized travel experiences encourages people to visit places they might not have considered otherwise, creating intense pressure on certain tourist hotspots. This phenomenon is particularly evident in small towns or remote areas that are not equipped to handle large numbers of tourists, leading to congestion and resource depletion.

Technological advancements in booking systems and peer-to-peer accommodation platforms such as Airbnb have also contributed to overtourism. These tools have made it easier and more affordable for tourists to plan trips, and they allow visitors to access areas that were once primarily residential. While this boosts local economies, it can also drive-up housing costs for locals and contribute to the displacement of residents. In cities like Barcelona and Venice, this shift has sparked protests from local communities, who feel they are being pushed out by the influx of tourists. Additionally, government policies and destination marketing campaigns often emphasize growth in tourism without considering sustainable limits. Governments see tourism as a quick way to boost the economy, often neglecting the long-term social and environmental costs. Aggressive marketing strategies aim to attract more tourists, overlooking the fact that some areas may already be

struggling to cope with current numbers. Overtourism is a complex issue driven by a combination of economic, technological, and cultural factors. The rise of budget travel, social media influence, the ease of booking accommodations, and short-term economic policies all contribute to the growing problem. To combat overtourism, it is crucial for governments, local communities, and the travel industry to implement sustainable tourism practices that balance economic benefits with the preservation of local cultures and environments. The causes of overtourism are presented in table 1.

Table 1. Causes of Overtourism

1	The accessibility and affordability of travel
2	The traditional policy focusing on promoting the number of tourists
3	Increase in international arrivals
4	The urbanization pressure
5	The gentrification and the increasing prices in city centers and new neighborhoods
6	The proliferation of unregulated tourist accommodation
7	The concentration of large groups of tourists
8	The decreasing cost of travelling
9	The sharing economy platforms
10	The fact that the use of public spaces is free for tourists
11	The strong seasonality
12	The reduced cost and travel time for transportation

Source: [4]

OVERCROWDED TOURISM DESTINATIONS AND OVERTOURISM IN A DESTINATION

The concepts of an overcrowded tourism destination and overtourism in a destination, while related, describe distinct aspects of tourism management and impact. Overcrowding refers specifically to the physical presence of too many tourists in a destination at a particular time, leading to immediate visible effects such as congested streets, long wait times at attractions, strained infrastructure, and reduced visitor experience. Overcrowded destinations are those where the sheer number of people exceeds the area's capacity to comfortably accommodate them, often during peak seasons or at popular tourist spots. Overtourism, on the other hand, goes beyond the momentary physical crowding of tourists. It describes the broader, often long-term, impact of tourism exceeding the social, environmental, and cultural carrying capacity of a destination. This phenomenon occurs when the volume of tourists negatively affects the quality of life for residents, damages ecosystems, erodes cultural heritage, and degrades the overall experience for both tourists and locals. Overtourism can lead to issues such as gentrification, displacement of local populations, pollution, and destruction of natural habitats. It is a more complex and systemic problem that involves unsustainable tourism practices and inadequate management of tourism growth over time. Overcrowding is more of a short-term, visible issue tied to a specific location or moment, while overtourism reflects a more extensive, often invisible strain that accumulates over time, affecting both the destination's sustainability and its social fabric. Overcrowding can contribute to overtourism, but addressing overtourism requires long-term strategies such as managing tourist numbers, promoting off-peak travel, and developing policies that protect both the destination and its local community from tourism-related pressures.

METHODS AND INDICATORS FOR ASSESSING OVERTOURISM

Overtourism, has prompted the development of various indexes to assess its impacts and inform better management practices. These indexes help policymakers, businesses, and local communities understand the extent of overtourism, guiding them toward sustainable solutions. By analyzing different dimensions such as environmental, economic, and social factors, these indexes offer comprehensive insights into how overtourism affects various destinations.

One of the most widely used tools to assess overtourism is the **Tourism Carrying Capacity (TCC)**. TCC measures the maximum number of visitors that a destination can accommodate without causing significant environmental or social damage. This index considers factors such as the ecological

resilience of natural sites, infrastructure capacity, and the well-being of local communities. For example, the number of tourists that a beach can support is assessed based on factors like waste management, erosion risk, and the availability of resources like freshwater. Although TCC is useful in setting thresholds, it can be difficult to establish an accurate capacity, as it varies based on the destination and changes over time.

Another important index is the **Resident Perception Index (RPI)**, which measures the satisfaction and attitudes of local residents toward tourism in their area. The RPI provides a snapshot of the social impacts of tourism by surveying residents on issues such as congestion, noise pollution, rising costs of living, and cultural changes. This index is particularly valuable in cities like Barcelona and Venice, where locals have expressed growing dissatisfaction with the negative consequences of overtourism. Monitoring resident attitudes helps policymakers understand when tourism has become unsustainable from a community perspective.

The **Environmental Impact Index (EII)** also plays a crucial role in assessing overtourism. It focuses on the degradation of natural environments due to tourist activities, measuring factors like air and water pollution, waste generation, and biodiversity loss. In ecologically sensitive areas such as national parks and coastal regions, the EII can highlight the extent to which tourism harms ecosystems. For instance, in destinations like the Galápagos Islands or the Great Barrier Reef, the EII is used to evaluate the effects of visitor numbers on endangered species and fragile ecosystems, guiding stricter conservation efforts.

Additionally, the **Tourism Intensity Index (TII)** is often employed to assess overtourism based on the ratio of tourists to local residents. This index is useful for comparing different destinations, as it calculates the density of tourists in relation to the local population. A high tourism intensity often indicates overcrowding, putting pressure on infrastructure and public services. For example, cities like Amsterdam and Dubrovnik have a high TII, highlighting the challenges of managing tourism in areas with small resident populations but massive tourist inflows. Indexes like the Tourism Carrying Capacity, Resident Perception Index, Environmental Impact Index, and Tourism Intensity Index provide essential tools for understanding and managing overtourism. By offering detailed insights into the environmental, social, and economic impacts of tourism, these indexes enable destinations to make informed decisions that balance tourism growth with sustainability and the well-being of local communities. Several indicators used in assessing overtourism are presented in table 2.

Table 2. Several Indicators for Assessing Overtourism

Category	Indicator
Tourism Intensity	Tourists/residents
	Beds/residents
	Bed-nights/residents
Tourism density	Tourists arriving by aircrafts/residents
	Tourists/km ²
	Bed-nights/km ²
Other indicators	Beds/km ²
	Tourists' revenue/GDP
	Airport and seaport closeness
	Air and sea transportation seasonality

Source: [16]

The most relevant indicators for assessing overtourism are [4]:

- a) Tourism density (bed-nights per km²) and intensity (bed-nights per resident),
- b) The share of Airbnb bed capacity of the combined Airbnb and booking.com bed capacity,
- c) The share of tourism in regional Gross Domestic Product (GDP),
- d) Air travel intensity (arrivals by air divided by number of residents) and
- e) Closeness to airport, cruise ports and UNESCO World Heritage Sites.

An overview of tourism densities and intensities are presented in table 3.

Table 3. Overview of Tourism Densities and Intensities in EU NUTS 2 Regions

	Tourism density (bed-nights/km ²)	Tourism intensity (Bed-nights/inhabitant)
Global average	181.8	3.31
Global min	6.4	0.00013
Global max	725,900	26.65
EU 28 average	629.3	5.77
EU28 min	26.1	0.34
EU28 max	37,300	70,73

Source: [4]

THE IMPACTS OF OVERTOURISM

Overtourism, has far-reaching impacts on the environment, local communities, and the tourism experience itself. As more people travel and concentrate in specific hotspots, the negative consequences become increasingly evident, threatening the long-term sustainability of these places. One of the most significant impacts of overtourism is environmental degradation. Many tourist destinations are located in areas of natural beauty, such as beaches, mountains, and national parks. When visitor numbers exceed the capacity of these ecosystems, the result is often habitat destruction, pollution, and loss of biodiversity. For example, coral reefs in places like Thailand's Maya Bay have been severely damaged by the sheer number of visitors, prompting authorities to close these sites for rehabilitation. The high volume of tourists can also lead to littering, increased carbon emissions, and overuse of natural resources like water, further straining fragile ecosystems. Another profound effect of overtourism is the disruption of local communities. As tourism grows, the demand for services such as accommodations, restaurants, and transportation rises, often pushing up the cost of living for local residents. In cities like Barcelona and Venice, locals have protested the negative effects of tourism on their neighborhoods, where short-term rentals have driven up housing prices, making it difficult for residents to afford living in their own cities. Moreover, the influx of tourists can erode the cultural fabric of a place, transforming traditional practices into commercialized spectacles designed for tourist consumption, ultimately diluting the authenticity of local cultures. The social impact of overtourism also extends to a loss of quality of life for both residents and tourists. Overcrowded streets, long queues at major attractions, and noise pollution from increased traffic all make daily life more difficult for locals. Meanwhile, tourists themselves often have less enjoyable experiences when they must navigate through packed destinations, encountering long waits and diminished access to the very attractions they came to see. This overcrowding can lead to "tourist fatigue," where local residents grow frustrated and less welcoming toward visitors, fostering resentment between the two groups. Economically, while tourism generates revenue, overtourism can lead to short-sighted development. The pursuit of quick profits sometimes overlooks the long-term sustainability of local economies. Seasonal jobs and over-reliance on tourism make local economies vulnerable to fluctuations, such as a sudden decline in tourist numbers due to pandemics or economic downturns. Overtourism has a range of negative impacts, from environmental degradation and cultural dilution to the erosion of local quality of life. To address these challenges, there is a growing need for sustainable tourism practices that respect both the environment and the well-being of local communities, ensuring that travel remains a positive force for all involved. The impacts of overtourism are presented in table 4.

Table 4. Impacts of Overtourism

Environmental	Overcrowding of infrastructure facilities and activities
	Overcrowding at attractions (natural, historical, et cetera)
	Strong contribution on pollution
	Damage to natural, historical, architectural sites
	Visual pollution
	High tourism-generated investments in tourism infrastructure

	Inflation or/and reduction in availability of goods and services
Economic	Degradation of commercial infrastructure
	Degradation of destination image
	Economic dependence on tourism
	Crowd-ness leading to a reduction of accessibility
Social	Marginalization of residents
	Problems related to uncivilized behavior and increased crime and violence
	Touristification of former residential neighborhoods
	Degradation of social infrastructure and facilities
	High possibility of misunderstanding
	Modification of several events and activities due to commercial interest
	Weakening of cultural traditions and values
	Decrease of the quality of life for the residents
	Lower quality of experience of tourists
	Increase in food prices
	Increase in house rentals
	Lack of houses for rent

Source: [4]

THE TOURISM INDUSTRY IN CRETE

Crete, the largest island in Greece, is a key destination for global tourism, attracting millions of visitors annually. Its tourism industry is vital to both the local and national economies, offering a blend of rich cultural history, breathtaking landscapes, and diverse recreational opportunities. One of the major draws of Crete is its extensive history. The island is home to some of the world's most significant archaeological sites, including the ancient Minoan civilization's palace of Knossos, which dates back to 1900 BC. This deep connection to the past, combined with picturesque Venetian harbors and Byzantine monasteries, offers visitors a unique cultural experience that sets Crete apart from other destinations. Crete also boasts a diverse and stunning natural environment. Its coastline stretches over 1,000 kilometers, offering an array of pristine beaches, crystal-clear waters, and dramatic cliffs. The interior of the island, with its rugged mountain ranges and gorges such as Samaria, provides excellent opportunities for hiking and eco-tourism. This variety of landscapes allows Crete to cater to all types of tourists, from those seeking relaxation by the sea to adventure enthusiasts. The island's tourism industry has also embraced sustainable tourism. Many local businesses promote eco-friendly practices, such as using locally sourced food, reducing plastic use, and supporting small, family-owned hotels and restaurants. This trend towards sustainability helps preserve the island's natural beauty and ensures that future generations of tourists can enjoy Crete's offerings. However, despite its success, Crete faces challenges in managing the growing number of tourists while protecting its fragile environment and local culture. Over-tourism, particularly in the peak summer months, can strain local resources and impact the island's ecosystems. The tourism industry in Crete plays a critical role in the island's development. Balancing growth with sustainability is key to ensuring that Crete remains a world-class destination for years to come. The tourism accommodations in Crete are presented in table 5.

Table 5. Tourism Accommodations in Crete (2021)

Hotels	1,644
Rooms	98,547
Beds	193,928
% , accommodations in Crete to accommodations in Greece	22.1%

Source: [13]

EVALUATING OVERTOURISM IN CRETE

The overtourism in Crete is evaluated and assessed estimating the tourism density and tourism intensity in the previous years. Due to Covid-19 pandemic data from 2020 and 2021 are not included. The increasing number of tourists in 2022 indicates that the tourism industry in Crete has recovered from the pandemic in 2022 earlier than in other tourism destinations. The estimated values are higher

than the EU and global average presented in table 3. It should be noted that the tourism infrastructure in Crete is unequally developed on the north coastline of the island while the inland and the south coastline are poorly developed. However, in our estimations the total residents and the total surface of the island have been used. The majority of visitors in Crete are arriving with aircrafts often from long distances while less of them are arriving by sea boats and cruise ships. The number of Airbnb beds are increasing every year in Crete competing the conventional hotel accommodations. Although fifty years ago agriculture was the main source of income in Crete nowadays tourism industry generates more than 50% of the regional income in the island. The tourism density and the tourism intensity in Crete are presented in table 6 while the change of tourism density and intensity over time in table 7.

Table 6. Tourism Density and Intensity in Crete

Surface of Crete	8,336 Km ²
Residents in Crete (Census 2021)	617,360 residents
Arrivals in Crete in 2023	6,327,366 tourists
% ,arrivals in Crete to arrivals in Greece in 2023	17.7 %
% ,increase in arrivals 2023/2022	7.2%
Overnight staying in Crete in 2023	34,342,891 (bed-nights)
% ,overnight staying in Crete to overnight staying in Greece in 2023	23.3 %
% ,increase in overnight staying 2023/2022	7.2%
Average days of staying in Crete in 2023	5.43 days
Tourism density	4,120 (bed-nights/km ²)
Tourism intensity	55.63 (Bed-nights/resident)

Source: own estimations, [31], [32], [33]

Table 7. Change of Tourism Density and Intensity Over Time in Crete

Year	Arrivals	Overnight staying (days)	Tourism density (bed-nights/km ²)	Tourism intensity (Bed-nights/resident)
2016	4,902,194		3,013	36.80
2019	5,033,786	5.56	3,354	45.29
2022	5,905,137	5.42	3,842	51.87
2023	6,327,366	5.43	4,120	55.63

Source: [14], [31], [13], [32], [33]

DISCUSSION

The phenomenon of overtourism is complex and multidimensional having many causes and impacts. The impacts can be categorized as environmental, economic and social. Overtourism represents the negative impacts of tourism affecting adversely the quality of life of the residents and the fragile ecosystems in the island. It also decreases the quality of experience of the visitors. Several indicators have been proposed by experts regarding the assessment of overtourism while two of them, including tourism density and tourism intensity, have been used in the present work to measure overtourism in the island of Crete, Greece. The number of visitors in Crete increases every year excluding the years 2020 and 2021 due to Covid-19 pandemic. The majority of tourism accommodations are located in the north coastline of Crete where the major cities are also located. During the peak tourism period the main cities in Crete are overcrowded. The high number of visitors has adverse environmental, economic and social impacts on the island. It has been indicated in several studies that there are not common agreed policies for overtourism mitigation in several popular tourism destinations. Tourism is nowadays the main driver of new jobs in Crete compared to agriculture and industry while the preferences of the majority of visitors are related with the three S, "Sea, Sun and Sand" tourism. The estimated tourism density and tourism intensity in Crete are above the EU and global average indicating that the high number of visitors could have adverse impacts on the local society and the fragile natural ecosystems which are also threatened by climate crisis. The limitations in our work are related with the evaluation of only two indexes assessing overtourism in Crete. Additional parameters, which have been indicated by experts [16], should be

estimated in order to have a better assessment of overtourism in Crete. Further research should be focused on evaluating several additional indexes for better assessment of overtourism in Crete. It should also investigate the appropriate response of the local tourism stakeholders regarding the necessary policies and measures to mitigate the undesired and harmful impacts of overtourism in the island.

CONCLUSIONS

The island of Crete, Greece is a popular global tourism destination hosting more than 5 million tourists every year. The majority of tourists are arriving during the summer months while the duration of the tourist season is not more than seven months annually. An analysis and assessment of overtourism in Crete has been realized. The number of tourists visiting the island is increasing every year. During 2023 6,327,366 tourists arrived in the island while the number of bed-nights was at 34,342,891. The average staying of tourists in 2023 in Crete was at 5.43 days. The tourism density in Crete in 2023 has been estimated at 4,120 bed-nights/km² while its tourism intensity at 55.63 bed-nights/resident. The high tourism density and intensity in Crete indicate that the growing tourism industry will have harmful environmental, economic and social impacts in the natural ecosystems and in local society. These harmful impacts should be mitigated in order to avoid the future decline of the prosperous tourism industry in the island. Our results could be useful to all stakeholders of the local tourism industry who should be mobilized to prevent the undesired impacts of overtourism in the island creating policies and measures promoting the sustainable and responsible tourism in Crete.

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